

Rice reactions to blast at Chiayi nursery, 1976.

Crop season	Plant type	Leaf blast				Neck blast			
		Resistant		Susceptible		Resistant		Susceptible	
		(no.)	(%)	(no.)	(%)	(no.)	(%)	(no.)	(%)
First	Ponlai	21	22.3	94	11.7	35	31.3	77	68.7
	Indica	42	11.8	12	22.2	45	84.9	8	15.1
Second	Ponlai	18	14.9	103	85.1	15	62.0	46	38.0
	Indica	13	24.1	41	75.9	16	30.2	37	69.8

rices. But now blast is often found in the second crop of the hot season, and indica rices are as susceptible as the ponlais. In the 1976 uniform blast nursery conducted at the Chiayi Station, 27 of 121 elite ponlais (22%) and 42 of 54 modern indicas (78%) in the first crop showed resistance to leaf blast, while 35 ponlais (31%) and 45 indicas (85%) were resistant to neck blast. In the second crop, however, entries resistant to blast decreased sharply with the

exception of ponlais that were resistant to neck blast. Only 18 ponlais (15%) and 13 indicas (24%) remained resistant to leaf blast, while 75 ponlais (62%) and 16 indicas (30%) were resistant to neck blast. These reactions indicate that rice varieties, particularly indicas, may tend to become more susceptible to blast under the environmental conditions of the second crop. Further observation on the seasonal change of rice reactions to blast appears necessary. ❧

5 or 11 weeks. Infection at 5 weeks after transplanting was assumed to stimulate formation of new tillers, while infection at 11 weeks after transplanting led to high larval mortality caused by plant vigor. The relation between damaged tillers (at 3 weeks after infection) and grain yield reduction indicated that each percentage unit of plant damage caused about 1 percent reduction in yield. ❧

Yield losses and economic injury levels of rice insect pests in South Sulawesi, Indonesia

Summary of a seminar presented by P. van Halteren at the Research Institute at Maros, Indonesia, April, 1977

Rice yield losses due to insects were assessed in South Sulawesi. When crops are not protected, rice insects (excluding the rice seedbug) reduce the potential yield of varieties such as Pelita I-1, C4-63, IR5, IR20, IR26, SPR 6726-76-2-3, and B462c-Pn-1-3 by from 1 to 3 t/ha, or an average of about 30%.

When the insect pests *Hydrellia philippina*, *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*, *Nymphula stagnalis*, *Spodoptera* spp., and grasshoppers attack rice during the first 4 weeks, yields may be cut by from 5 to 10%. *Cnaphalocrosis* attacks in the flag leaf stage might also cut yields by from 5 to 10%.

Artificial defoliation produced the greatest loss at about 7 to 10 weeks after transplanting, during the periods of panicle initiation and formation.

Measuring the effect of stem borers during the vegetative stage was complicated; deadheart percentages seemed to be a poor indication of damage and the data were inconclusive. During the reproductive stage, yield losses due to stem borers varied from 0.9 to 2.1% per unit percent of whitehead, or an average of 1.2%.

Studies of yield loss from the rice bug resulted in the regression line $y = 11.34 \log x - 7.34$ ($r = 0.676$ and $n = 36$), indicating that yield loss can be expected at a certain population density. Chemical treatment seems justified if from 1 to 2 bugs/sq m are found. ❧

Pest management and control INSECTS

Relation between damage by rice stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* and yield of rice variety Pelita I-1

J. Soejitno, Entomology Department, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Bogor, Indonesia

The yellow rice borer *Tryporyza incertulas* is a pest of major importance in Indonesia. Insecticide application is based primarily upon the rice plant stages. To be economically justified, such applications should be based on insect population density.

A study was conducted to determine the relationship between percentage of tillers damaged by *T. incertulas* and grain yield. The experiment was conducted in a screenhouse with four 2- × 2-m plots. Rice variety Pelita I-1 was grown at a planting distance of 20 × 20 cm. Plots were artificially infected with newly hatched *T. incertulas* larvae at 5, 7, 9, or 11 weeks after transplanting. Deadhearts were counted weekly. Data on whiteheads and grain yield were based upon hill units.

Rice grain yield of Pelita I-1 related to the tillers that were damaged by the larvae of yellow stem borer *T. incertulas*. (WT = weeks after transplanting)

Data on damage and grain yield indicated that the relation between stem borer damage and rice yield is linear rather than exponential (see figure).

Damage in plots infected at 7 and 9 weeks after transplanting may cause higher yield reduction than damage at